

EUREMAP demonstrator project: Enhancing the Production and Therapeutic Potential of Streptocyclinones for Alzheimer's Disease.

Version 8

Description

The EUREMAP project aims to optimise the marine bioprospecting workflow within the European research community, enabling state-of-the-art research and enhanced capacity for academia and industry. This will be achieved by building upon the existing expertise available within the consortium members (EU OPENSREEN, EMBL, EMBRC, ELIXIR) to synergise capacities and resources to enhance marine bioprospecting for natural products.

The EUREMAP platform to be developed will consist of a new multidisciplinary marine bioprospecting workflow that integrates the existing technical capacities, thereby increasing the competitiveness of marine natural products in drug discovery and strengthening the blue bioeconomy in line with the European blue growth strategy. The functioning EUREMAP marine bioprospecting workflow will support the discovery of novel bioactive natural products from marine organisms by utilising novel technology to improve the capacity of European Research infrastructures (RIs). The multidisciplinary nature of the marine bioprospecting research space necessarily requires integrating data flows between disparate research fields. As such, while data management components within disciplines may be in place, they may not be adequately formulated to provide the basis for a cohesive and integrated data workflow.

The following dataset descriptions are specific to the **EUREMAP demonstrator project: Enhancing the Production and Therapeutic Potential of Streptocyclinones for Alzheimer's Disease.**

The project focuses on identifying and characterizing additional streptocyclinones present in the cultures of the marine *Streptomyces* sp. CA-237351. Known members of the streptocyclinone family have anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties). We aim to deepen the understanding of their biosynthesis and potential therapeutic applications and expand the known diversity of streptocyclinone variants.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

European Research
Infrastructure for Marine
Bioprospecting
(corda_____he::101131663)

Researchers

Stéphane Bach (0000-0002-7186-7483), Marcelino Suzuki (0000-0003-3868-6362), Fernando Reyes (0000-0003-1607-5106), Olga Genilloud (0000-0002-4202-1219), Jose Santiago Sanchez Fragoso (0000-0001-7018-3891)

Organizations

Fundación Centro de Excelencia en Investigación de
Medicamentos Innovadores en Andalucía, SORBONNE

UNIVERSITE, European Molecular Biology Laboratory, Centre
National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), Paris

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: EUREMAP demonstrator project: Enhancing the Production and Therapeutic Potential of Streptocyclinones for Alzheimer's Disease.

Description:

The EUREMAP project aims to optimise the marine bioprospecting workflow within the European research community, enabling state-of-the-art research and enhanced capacity for academia and industry. This will be achieved by building upon the existing expertise available within the consortium members (EU OPENSREEN, EMBL, EMBRC, ELIXIR) to synergise capacities and resources to enhance marine bioprospecting for natural products.

The EUREMAP platform to be developed will consist of a new multidisciplinary marine bioprospecting workflow that integrates the existing technical capacities, thereby increasing the competitiveness of marine natural products in drug discovery and strengthening the blue bioeconomy in line with the European blue growth strategy. The functioning EUREMAP marine bioprospecting workflow will support the discovery of novel bioactive natural products from marine organisms by utilising novel technology to improve the capacity of European Research infrastructures (RIs). The multidisciplinary nature of the marine bioprospecting research space necessarily requires integrating data flows between disparate research fields. As such, while data management components within disciplines may be in place, they may not be adequately formulated to provide the basis for a cohesive and integrated data workflow.

The following dataset descriptions are specific to the **EUREMAP demonstrator project: Enhancing the Production and Therapeutic Potential of Streptocyclinones for Alzheimer's Disease.**

The project focuses on identifying and characterizing additional streptocyclinones present in the cultures of the marine *Streptomyces* sp. CA-237351. Known members of the streptocyclinone family have anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties). We aim to deepen the understanding of their biosynthesis and potential therapeutic applications and expand the known diversity of streptocyclinone variants.

Researchers:

Stéphane Bach (0000-0002-7186-7483)

Marcelino Suzuki (0000-0003-3868-6362)

Fernando Reyes (0000-0003-1607-5106)

Olga Genilloud (0000-0002-4202-1219)

Jose Santiago Sanchez Fragoso (0000-0001-7018-3891)

Organizations:

Fundación Centro de Excelencia en Investigación de Medicamentos Innovadores en Andalucía

SORBONNE UNIVERSITE

European Molecular Biology Laboratory

Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), Paris

Contact: Genilloud Olga (olga.genilloud@medinaandalucia.es)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: European Research Infrastructure for Marine Bioprospecting (corda___he::101131663)

Project: EUREMAP: European Research Infrastructure for Marine Bioprospecting

3. License

License: CC-BY-SA-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Biomass production: Cultivation Protocol

Biomass Production: SU - Scaled-up cultivation and identification of the best conditions for production of additional molecules (OSMAC).

Data Management Plan | EUREMAP demonstrator project: Enhancing the Production and Therapeutic Potential of Streptocyclinones for Alzheimer's Disease. LICENSE:CC-BY-SA-4.0 DOI: - 23/06/2026

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

We will create new protocols that are specific to the instrumentation available in our facility and as far as we know these protocols are not available for reuse.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

Protocols, so the options are not applicable

1.1.5 What is its format?

pdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3Gb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

Other

We will mostly need this data for reproducibility sake

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Our own records (laboratory notebooks) which will be compiled optimized and summarized in a single protocol

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

Other researchers and industry will use this data to reproduce or adapt future protocols

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

protocols.io repository will provide a DOI to the published protocol.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/MCO>

Microbial Conditions Ontology contains terms to describe growth conditions in microbiological experiments.

A specific vocabulary has not been created, a similar one is mentioned in <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9265904/>.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

protocols.io

<https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/euremap-protocols-community>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

We will use the EUREMAP Protocols Community as a library of service protocols, <https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/euremap-protocols-community>

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes, assign the DOI to the published protocols.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Protocols for the production of bioactive molecules from Bacteria in small (2L) bioreactors

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

This might change at the end of the project if industrial exploration is not pursued

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Possible industrial exploitation of the results

3.2.2.4 If an embargo applies, please specify when the dataset / output will be made available.

2026-10-01

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

through the protocols.io website if open

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

as far as we know eternally

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2026-10-01

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

n/a

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The original Biosamples ID of the samples of the dataset description "A list of biomass samples from marine Streptomyces sp. CA-237351 with production conditions" will be referenced for provenance purposes.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Other

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

1

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use
- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Marcelino Suzuki (0000-0003-3868-6362)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Passwords
- Other

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Publication in EUREMAP Protocols Community at protocols.io

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Chemical extraction: Green extraction and purification of both, known and novel streptocyclinones.

Protocols for the extraction and chromatographic fractionation of cultures of *Streptomyces* sp. producing known and novel streptocyclinones.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Protocols

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Data will be generated from new samples obtained during the development of the project.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

Protocols will include a description of the experimental process followed for the extraction and purification of new compounds

1.1.5 What is its format?

PDF files

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

30 Mb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To keep on record

To share information on procedures used for the purification of streptocyclinones

To keep on record of experimental conditions and other details

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Instruments used in the fractionation of extracts and lab notebooks

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

Data might be useful to reproduce the process in the future by other researchers in an academic or industrial settings.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Once deposited, data will be available through a DOI Assigned by the database

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata will include origin and type of data

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

Those required by Protocols

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Metadata will be described in the Protocols.io (EUREMAP Protocols Community), which provides search capabilities.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Protocols.io

<https://www.protocols.io/>

A secure platform for developing and sharing reproducible methods.

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Agreement to the terms of use and submission as set out by Protocols.io

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Protocols for the extraction of microbial cultures and the fractionation of extracts

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The database is open to all researchers

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset and associated metadata will be available (longterm) via the Protocols repository once all the IP and publication issues have been solved

Through registration in Protocols

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Datasets will be available forever through Protocols

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Datasets will be open after an embargo period

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Not relevant because data will be stored in a permanent repository

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

The vocabulary standards required by Protocols.io

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Standard required by Protocols.io

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

After IP or publication issues have been solved

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

Instructions from Protocols.io

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Protocols.io is open access

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Data will be originated from LIMS and lab notebooks.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

Data need to be uploaded to the database in a standard format

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Indirect cost

Use of MEDINA infrastructure, considered an in kind contribution

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

In kind contribution

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Mercedes Pérez-Bonilla, Senior Researcher, ORCID: 0000-0001-8544-0862

Fernando Reyes, Head of Chemistry, ORCID: 0000-0003-1607-5106

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Data will be in Protocols repository

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Structural Elucidation: NMR

1D and 2D NMR data of natural products isolated from extracts of microbial sources

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Data will be generated from compounds purified during the development of the project

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

The data set consists of primary NMR data generated by the instrument

Secondary data will include NMR tables and structures of the compounds

1.1.5 What is its format?

Bruker specific format readable by commercial and free access tools for NMR data

SMILES for structures

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

About 80 Mb per compound

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To combine with other data

To obtain information necessary to elucidate the structure of the molecules obtained during the development of the project.

To share information useful to other researchers to verify the identity of the compounds isolated in their own research.

To keep on record of compounds NMR spectra

To combine with HRMS data to solve the structure of new compounds

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Compounds belonging to the streptocyclinone structural class purified during the development of the project.

Compounds will be originated from Biomass extracts having an ID through a process registered in a LIMS system available at the institution. Unique ID identifiers will be generated for each compound.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

Researchers and research communities to verify the identity of their compounds

Industry for the same purpose in an industrial set up.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://www.bruker.com/en/products-and-solutions/mr/nmr-software/topspin.html>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Once deposited, data will be available through a DOI Assigned by the database

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata will include name and structure of the compound, species of origin, and experimental conditions used in the acquisition of the NMR data.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://np-mrd.org/>

Those required by NP-MRD

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Metadata will be deposited in NP-MRD database which provides search capabilities

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

NP-MRD

<https://np-mrd.org/>

The NP-MRD is a freely available cloud-based, user-friendly, FAIR electronic database. NP-MRD accepts NMR data and associated metadata from newly undertaken NP studies. The NP-MRD accepts raw (time domain data, processed spectra, assigned chemical shifts, J-couplings, RDCs, etc.), and meta-data (structures, sources, methods, taxonomy, geospatial data, etc) from natural products ranging from purified substances to crude extracts, in all major solvents. The NP-MRD include NPs such as vitamins, minerals, and probiotics as well as small molecules derived from plants, fungi, bacteria, marine organisms, or animals. The NP-MRD accepts, converts, and stores all major vendor NMR formats and all major NMR data exchange formats from all common NMR experiments as well as new/uncommon NMR experiments or data sets. The NP-MRD have an intuitive user interface for spectra/structure deposition, retrieval, search, and analysis. Data deposition is fast (<5 min/per spectrum), easy and intuitive, and aided by online assignment and online spectra/structure visualization tools. Structure and assignment validation reports are generated within 5 minutes of deposition and value-added data reports are provided to users within 24 hrs of deposition, including high-quality DFT calculations of chemical shifts for a deposited structure. Data integrity and data quality are ensured by extensive curation efforts and the use of an objective ranking scale for all deposited data.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Agreement to the terms of use and submission as set out by NP-MRD

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

NMR data of compound ID (NP-MRD ID)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The database is open to all researchers

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset and associated metadata will be available (longterm) via the NP-MRD repository once all the IP and publication issues have been solved

Through registration in NP-MRD

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Datasets will be available forever through NP-MRD

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Datasets will be open after an embargo period

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

Not relevant because data will be stored in a permanent repository

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Vocabulary required by NP-MRD

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Standard required by NP-MRD

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

After IP or publication issues have been solved

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

Instructions from NP-MRD

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The NP-MRD is open

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Data will be originated from LIMS and lab notebooks. Biosamples ID

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

Data need to be uploaded to the database in a standard format

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage

- Archiving

- Re-use

Indirect cost

Use of MEDINA infrastructure, considered an in kind contribution

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure

- Other

In kind contribution

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Francisco Javier Ortiz-Lopez, Senior Researcher, ORCID: 0000-0002-9410-3718

Fernando Reyes, Head of Chemistry, ORCID: 0000-0003-1607-5106

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Data will be in NP-MRD repository

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Structural Elucidation: LC-MS

LC/HRMS and LC/MS/MS data necessary to determine the molecular formula of the new compounds and key fragments to contribute to their structural elucidation.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Reusing of existing data is not applicable to the context of this study.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

The dataset consists of **primary** and **secondary** mass spectrometry data generated from LC-MS and LC/MS/MS based experiments.

Primary data includes raw m/z values, retention times, intensity values and mass spectra, while **secondary data** includes processed tabular data derived from the raw measurements.

1.1.5 What is its format?

- **Raw data:** vendor-specific format converted to .mzML
- **Pre-processed data:** feature/peak in tabular format (.csv), pre-processed structured data in SQLite format for relational queries, and pre-processed data for posterior storing and annotations in JSON format.
- **Metabolite ID data:** annotated metabolite tables (.csv, SQLite, JSON); Spectral match data (if storing MS/MS matches; .mgf)
- **Quantitative data:** processed intensity data, peak areas or relative abundances (.csv, SQLite, JSON)
- **Statistical Data:** tabular, json and SQLite, R script

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

~10–50 GB for a small scale study (up to 50 samples)

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
 - To share information
 - To keep on record
 - To make informed decisions
 - To combine with other data
- **to obtain information:** collection of mass spectrometry data to establish the molecular formula of new compounds
 - **to share information:** making the data available for the scientific community to foster collaboration and enable researchers to build upon existing datasets; allowing fellow researchers to compare their findings with the shared data; to support metabolomics-driven advancements

- **to keep on record:** to permit for long-term accessibility and compliance; to support future reanalysis & method development; to facilitate data traceability
- **to make informed decisions:** to guide experimental design and hypothesis refinement, enhancing biological interpretation and clinical/industrial applications; to optimize resource allocation
- **to combine with** NMR data for the structural elucidation of compounds

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Compounds belonging to the streptocyclinone structural class purified during the development of the project.

Compounds will be originated from Biomass extracts having an ID through a process registered in a LIMS system available at the institution. Unique ID identifiers will be generated for each compound.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
 - Research communities
 - The public
 - Industry
- **Researchers and research communities to verify the identity of their compounds**
 - **Industry for the same purpose in an industrial set up.**

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Once deposited, data will be available through a DOI Assigned by the database

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

"MetaboLights adheres to MSI standards for metadata reporting and uses the ISA-tab format [6] to capture and study metadata, including the metabolites identified or annotated."

ISA-Tab:

The Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) tab-delimited (TAB) format is a general purpose framework with which to collect and communicate complex metadata (i.e. sample characteristics, technologies used, type of measurements made) from 'omics-based' experiments employing a combination of technologies.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/msio>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Metadata, by being submitted in MetaboLights, is a query available for search engines.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata that is stored on the MetaboLights Repository is harvestable: MetaboLights provides an application programming interface to enable programmatic access to metabolomics datasets, which allows researchers to retrieve study metadata, search for studies based on keywords and download raw and processed data.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

MetaboLights

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

MetaboLights is a database for Metabolomics experiments and derived information. The database is cross-species, cross-technique and covers metabolite structures and their reference spectra as well as their biological roles, locations and concentrations, and experimental data from metabolic experiments. MetaboLights is the recommended Metabolomics repository for a number of leading journals.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Assigns PIDs
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Agreement to the terms of use and submission as set out by MetaboLights

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

- Initially, MetaboLights will issue a temporary submission request (i.e. REQxxx). Upon passing validation, a full MetaboLights accession number (i.e. MTBLSxxx) will be assigned, which does not change over time
- the accession number is resolved to a web-accessible dataset page

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

LC-MS Metabolomic Profiling

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Data will be accesible forever through Metabolights

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Metadata will always be available, even if the dataset was not.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Not applicable as metadata and data will be available longterm on MetaboLights.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

The instructions within the checklist for submission (MetaboLights) of both metadata and data will be followed.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

ISA-Tab format

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

(Meta)data of metabolomics experiments and derived information is stored in MetaboLighs in ISA-Tab format

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Metabolomics data and metadata submitted to MetaboLights will be linked to a BioSamples ID.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

After IP or publication issues have been solved

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Other

Instructions from Metabolights

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

It is accessible on the repository with the appropriate licence.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Biosamples ID

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

Data need to be uploaded to the database in a standard format

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Use of MEDINA infrastructure, considered an in kind contribution

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

In kind contribution

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Jesús M. Martín Serrano, Senior Researcher, ORCID: 0000-0001-7487-2790

Fernando Reyes, Head of Chemistry, ORCID: 0000-0003-1607-5106

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Data will be in Metabolights repository

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

unknown

This will be evaluated by the ethical committee

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Bioassays/Bioprofiling: Protein Kinase Assays

Assessment of the bioactivity of marine extracts and compounds using protein kinase screening: a target-based approach. Protein kinases are enzymes involved in the regulation of key cellular processes, such as metabolism, cell migration and cycle progression, vascular functions and angiogenesis and neuroplasticity. The dysregulation of a broad range of protein kinases leads to numerous diseases including cancer, nervous and inflammatory disorders. As such, **kinases have become prime drug targets**. More than 80 kinase inhibitors have been approved by FDA/EMA in haematology and oncology. The search for marine-sourced protein-kinase inhibitors has proven to be extremely successful with bioactive compounds already entering pharmaceutical development and others exerting strong activities against a range of kinases heavily involved in an increasing list of disease mechanisms. In order to **characterize new active chemical structures from marine microorganisms**, the natural extracts can be tested against a panel of **protein kinases involved in tau phosphorylation-related neurodegenerative disease** (such as **CDK5/p25, GSK3alpha and beta isoforms, DYRK1A and CLK1**). This kinase assays and the results produced will be described here.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

The data generated are primary data that will be collected for the first time.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Tabular data with minimal metadata column headings, variable names. MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) converted to text tab format such as .csv.

Image data. JPEG format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

approx. 5 Mb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

These data are generated to identify a bioactive chemical compound inside a marine natural extract. Once the product is identified, these data are used to compare its bioactivity to those of chemical derivatives or of other bioactive compounds already identify. **The objective is to identify the more active**

compound to be use in preclinical and clinical assays for treatment of neurodegenerative disorders including Alzheimer's disease.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The compounds to be tested are from marine natural resources (e.g. marine derived actinomycete strains) and provided by chemists.

Link to original sample with biosamples ID.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry

The data will be used by academic or private researchers to **develop new active ingredients from marine resources**. The main objective is to **improve the treatment of neurodegenerative disorders** by inhibition of protein kinases involved in the pathological process.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://www.graphpad.com/features>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Projects identifiers

arXiv

ORCID

Other

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

PUBCHEM_RESULT_TAG	PUBCHEM_EXT_DATASOURCE_REGID	PUBCHEM_ACTIVITY_OUTCOME	Hits	Chemical name	MW	IC50
RESULT_DESCR						
RESULT_TYPE			STRING	STRING	INTEGER	FLOAT
RESULT_UNIT						MICROMOLAR
1	myid-L2-04	2	L2-04	ethyl 3-(pyridin-2-ylthio)propanoate	211	2.6
2	myid-CS	1	CS	(4R)-4-amino-3-isoxazolidinone	102	58
3	myid-L2-05	2	L2-05	N-benzyl-5-chloro-2-methylsulfonylpyrimidine-4-carboxamide	326	6.8

Image 1

PUBCHEM_EXT_DATASOURCE_REGID

Supply Identifiers (RegIDs) For Each Tested Row

PUBCHEM_SUBSTANCE_SYNONYM

If these chemical names are found in PubChem Substance, their structures can be retrieved and all associated properties and weighted synonyms used to further increase the exposure of your tested results.

PUBCHEM_ACTIVITY_OUTCOME

PubChem maintains a special Outcome field which lets the submitter make a judgement call on whether to consider each data row inactive or active. A simple integer code is used with 1 for inactive and 2 for active

Hits

ID defined by the screening team (e.g. L2-04)

Chemical name

Chemical name of the tested compounds (e.g. ethyl 3-(pyridin-2-ylthio)propanoate)

MW

Molecular weight of the tested compound (e.g. 211)

IC50

IC50 Value for the tested compound (e.g. 2.6)

There are **optional headers** that allow you to specify the result type (integer, float, string, etc.) and unit (% , uMol, etc.) of each test result defined, but these can be entered later.

RESULT_DESCR

The RESULT_DESCR row lets you add an optional description for each test result to help the user better understand what it is and how it was determined. We indicate here the ID of the tested kinase. Note that certain special types are allowed such as PUBCHEM_NCBI_GENE_ID which will automatically generate links to the other database in your data table.

RESULT_TYPE

The second of the optional Result definition rows is the RESULT_TYPE. It lets the researchers define a type so that errors can more easily be identified and so that plotting tools can be used on the numerical parts of the data. If the type is not specified, STRING type is assumed.

RESULT_UNIT

The third of the optional Result definition rows is the RESULT_UNIT. It lets the researchers define a unit where appropriate. In our case, only the IC50 column had a unit. Only INTEGER and FLOAT types can have units.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

use bioassay ontology as required by pubchem.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<http://bioassayontology.org/>

Kinase: An enzyme that catalyzes the transfer of a phosphate group from ATP to specific substrates, often regulating their activity.

ATP (Adenosine Triphosphate): The primary energy carrier in cells, formed through processes like oxidative and substrate-level phosphorylation

Protein kinases are enzymes that modify other proteins by adding phosphate groups to them, a process known as phosphorylation. This action plays a critical role in regulating various cellular processes, including cell signaling,

metabolism, and gene expression, making protein kinases essential components in eukaryotic translational and post-translational gene regulation.

Protein kinase inhibitor: It is a type of enzyme inhibitor that can block the action of protein kinases.

Primary Screening: analysis of the bioactivity by testing one or two doses of the molecule or natural extracts.

IC₅₀: The concentration of a drug, inhibitor or natural extract, needed to inhibit a biological process or response by 50%. IC₅₀ is commonly used as a measure of drug potency. IC₅₀ assays are also used for screening in target-based drug discovery campaigns.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

Accessible in the pubchem repository and/or in <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies>.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Accessible in the pubchem repository and/or <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies>.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

PubChem

PubChem is an open chemistry database at the National Institutes of Health (NIH). "Open" means that you can put your scientific data in PubChem and that others may use it. Since the launch in 2004, PubChem has become a key chemical information resource for scientists, students, and the general public. Each month our website and programmatic services provide data to several million users worldwide.

PubChem mostly contains small molecules, but also larger molecules such as nucleotides, carbohydrates, lipids, peptides, and chemically-modified macromolecules. We collect information on chemical structures, identifiers, chemical and physical properties, biological activities, patents, health, safety, toxicity data, and many others.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal

- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place
- Other

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

All the listed arrangements above.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Yes.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Inhibitory activity of purified compounds

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

Closed during the embargo time, then public access is possible via the repository Pubchem.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

As the data can be used to find new therapeutic compounds, an embargo period of two years must be applied to seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents) or of the time needed for the publication of the results (approx. 6-12 months). Note here that the results can be also published as preprint articles to speed up dissemination of the non-patentable discoveries.

3.2.2.4 If an embargo applies, please specify when the dataset / output will be made available.

2029-01-01

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

A data access committee should be constituted by **the leader of team who provided the fractions (chemists)** or natural extracts to the screening facility **and by the biologists who were able to show the bioactivity**. Together they decide if the data can be shared.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset will be submitted in pubchem and be public available after embargo time ends.

is publicly available in repository, it can accessed anonymously.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinitely.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Metadata information will be accessible in the repository, even during the embargo time.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Is all in the same repository.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

Both metadata and data will be available indefinitely in the public repository.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Bioassay ontology.

The ID used for the identification of the targets tested is a standardized terminology available on [Uniprot database](#): ex. GSK-3a (P49840).

UniProt is the world's leading high-quality, comprehensive and freely accessible resource of protein sequence and functional information.

The UniProt consortium and host institutions EMBL-EBI, SIB and PIR are committed to the long-term preservation of the UniProt databases.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

We follow the rules of the bioassay ontology and pubchem.

Biontology uses OWL.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Submit to a public established repository.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

Yes, o...

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

2029-01-01

Two years for a patent and up to one year for an scientific article.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The data produced will be available upon due date of the embargo.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

From the initial sample with biosamples ID to LIMS references IDs throughout the project pipeline.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

Laboratory notebook.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

Approximately 5,000 € (costs for storage of data on servers during 15 years)

Euro

Storage

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Stéphane Bach (0000-0002-7186-7483)

Contact also Thomas Robert (0000-0002-1076-7251)

or

Blandine Baratte (0000-0002-2064-9558)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Submission to pubchem.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Not available

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Biomass production: A list of biomass samples from marine *Streptomyces* sp. CA-237351 with production conditions

The data in this section refers to a table containing all individual biomass samples from fermentations (Growth in bioreactors) of the marine *Streptomyces* sp. CA-237351, including metadata on the conditions used for this production

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

this will be results of an ongoing demonstration project

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

results of growth of *Streptomyces* sp. CA-237351 under different conditions

1.1.5 What is its format?

a TSV file that could be used as a table in a relational database.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To combine with other data

This data will allow us in the end of the demonstration projet to identify and share the best production conditions for specific streptocyclinones that have a potential to be used as drug down the line

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data in the table will be weights in grams of dry or lyophilized material from bacterial cultures in bioreactors

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Industry

The identification of conditions maximizing yields of production will be of interests for researchers looking for new molecules as well as industry in case these molecules become products

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Projects identifiers

URL

Cordis

this will be one of the deliverables of WP4

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9265904/>

A specific vocabulary has not been created, a similar one is mentioned in the like above

or

<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/SBO>

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

BioStudies

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>

The BioStudies database holds descriptions of biological studies, links to data from these studies in other databases at EMBL-EBI or outside, as well as data that do not fit in the structured archives at EMBL-EBI. The database can accept a wide range of types of studies described via a simple format. It also enables manuscript authors to submit supplementary information and link to it from the publication.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Euremap Streptomyces Demonstration Project Biomass Production

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The possibility of industrialization of the results

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

We will share it to the sharepoint of the Project

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

The sample metadata will be available in Biosamples repository:
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

The sample metadata will be available in Biosamples repository:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Not available

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Marcelino Suzuki (0000-0003-3868-6362)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

sharepoints

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data sharing

Sharepoints

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Genomics: Biosynthetic Gene Cluster (BGC) predictions in genus *Streptomyces*

BGC predictions derived from using the BGCdetection pipeline on genomic isolates from genus *Streptomyces*.

This results will assist the EUREMAP demonstrator project: Enhancing the Production and Therapeutic Potential of Streptocyclinones for Alzheimer's Disease.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We will use data from genomic assemblies of strains from *Streptomyces* genus.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This process does not involve new observational or experimental data collection but rather relies on computational analysis to identify probable BGC regions within pre-existing data. These predictions are generated by recognising patterns

associated with biosynthetic potential, based on models trained on known BGCs from reference datasets.

1.1.5 What is its format?

GFF3

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product

We are generating and re-using data to support the identification of new natural products in marine genomic datasets. This information will help us characterise natural products from strains of interest.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data originates from the genomic assembly analysis of genome sequencing. These assemblies are sourced from a combination of public datasets and privately held datasets.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
 - Industry
- Researchers: Fields like microbiology, genomics, and natural products discovery can use this dataset to explore novel biosynthetic pathways, identify potential bioactive compounds, and conduct further analyses on gene clusters within marine environments.
 - Industry: Biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, and companies in the blue economy can utilise this dataset to accelerate the development of new molecules. For example, companies interested in natural bioactives for therapeutics or

industrial applications can utilise these predictions to guide experimental screening and compound extraction efforts.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

https://github.com/Finn-Lab/BGCdetection_pipeline

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

DOI

Our results accessions rely on an internal identifier system that is fully sufficient for managing and tracking data within our closed environment.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

- Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS)

- RO-Crate

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

• Descriptive metadata will outline what the data is about, providing context such as the subject and purpose for easy identification and understanding.

• Reference metadata will capture details on the version of the analysis pipelines, datasets used, and any processing steps, ensuring reproducibility and traceability across different stages of analysis.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

For BGC/Natural product classification we use standards vocabularies.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

- a. <https://docs.antismash.secondarymetabolites.org/glossary/>

When available, classification of BGC predictions are based on "Protocluster Types", defined by the antiSMASH team.

- b. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-018-0318-y>

When available, classification of BGC predictions are based on "Biosynthetic class", widely used in the BGC research community.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

No

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

BioStudies

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Predictions of Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGC) from genus Streptomyces

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Some of the results could hold IP value.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset will be shared internally, and deposited in BioStudies EMBL-EBI repository.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Ecosystem classification - https://gold.jgi.doe.gov/ecosystem_classification

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

An embargo period applies, the dataset will be made publicly available either upon the publication of a related paper or after a maximum period of three years, whichever comes first.

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

Depends on outcomes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Other

QC after data entry. Perform statistical summaries.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

5000

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

- Security

Indirect cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Jose Santiago Sanchez Fragoso (0000-0001-7018-3891)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Hash functions

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

unknown

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Unknown

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Powered by

